

Improved of Elliptic Curves Cryptography over a Ring

A. Chillali, A. Tadmori, M. Ziane

Abstract—In this article we will study the elliptic curve defined over the ring A_n and we define the mathematical operations of ECC, which provides a high security and advantage for wireless applications compared to other asymmetric key cryptosystem.

Keywords—Elliptic Curves, Finite Ring, Cryptography.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE ECC use curves whose variables coefficients are finite, there are two family commonly used on this cryptography. The first uses elliptic curves $E(\mathbb{F}_p)$ over prime finite field $\mathbb{F}_p$ where p is large prime; this family is the best for software implementation of ECC. The second family use elliptic curves $E(\mathbb{F}_{2^d})$ over binary field $\mathbb{F}_{2^d}$ where d is large integer number, this family is more suitable for hardware implementation of ECC. In this work, we define the other family which seems to be beneficial and interesting in ECC implementations. Its the family use elliptic curves $E_{a,b}(A_n)$ over the ring $A_n = \mathbb{F}_{2^d}[\varepsilon]$ where $\varepsilon^n = 0$, d and n are large integers numbers [1], [2], [7].

Let d be a positive integer, we consider the quotient ring $A_n = \frac{\mathbb{F}_{2^d}[X]}{(X^n)}$ where $\mathbb{F}_{2^d}$ is the finite field of order 2^d . The ring A_n is identified to the ring $\mathbb{F}_{2^d}[\varepsilon]; \varepsilon^n = 0$. So, we have: $A_n = \{\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i \varepsilon^i | (x_i)_{0 \leq i \leq n-1} \in \mathbb{F}_{2^d}^n\}$. Similar as in [3] and in [5], we have the following lemmas:

Lemma 1. The elements non invertible in the ring A_n are the elements of ideal εA_n .

Proof: A_n is a local ring, its maximal ideal is $M = \varepsilon A_n$.

Lemma 2. A_n is a vector space over $\mathbb{F}_{2^d}$ of dimension n and $(1, \varepsilon, \varepsilon^2, \varepsilon^3, \dots, \varepsilon^{n-1})$ is a basis of A_n .

Lemma 3. Let $Y = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_i \varepsilon^i$ be the inverse of the element $X = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i \varepsilon^i$ then:

$$\begin{cases} y_0 = x_0^{-1} \\ y_j = x_0^{-1} \cdot \sum_{i=0}^{j-1} y_i x_{j-i}. \text{ For } j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1. \end{cases}$$

II. NOTATION

Definition 1. We define an elliptic curve over the ring A_n noted $E_{a,b}(A_n)$ as a curve given by such Weierstrass equation:

$$Y^2Z + XYZ = X^3 + aX^2Z + bZ^3 \quad (1)$$

where $a, b \in A_n$ that b is invertible.

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The discriminant $\Delta = b$ and the J-invariant $J = \frac{1}{b}$, we write:

$$E_{a,b}(A_n) = \{[X:Y:Z] \in \mathbb{P}_2(A_n) | Y^2Z + XYZ = X^3 + aX^2Z + bZ^3\}$$

Definition 2. We define a reduction of $E_{a,b}(A_n)$ over $\mathbb{F}_{2^d}$ as a curve given by such Weierstrass equation:

$$Y^2Z + XYZ = X^3 + a_0X^2Z + b_0Z^3 \quad (2)$$

where $a_0, b_0 \in \mathbb{F}_{2^d}$ that $b_0 \neq 0$.

The discriminant $\Delta_0 = b_0$ and the j-invariant $j = \frac{1}{b_0}$, we write:

$$E_{a_0,b_0}(\mathbb{F}_{2^d}) = \{[X:Y:Z] \in \mathbb{P}_2(\mathbb{F}_{2^d}) | Y^2Z + XYZ = X^3 + a_0X^2Z + b_0Z^3\}$$

Notation 1. We denote π the canonical projection by:

$$\pi: A_n \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_{2^d} \\ \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i \varepsilon^i \mapsto x_0$$

III. CLASSIFICATION OF ELEMENTS OF $E_{a,b}(A_2)$

Let $[X:Y:Z] \in E_{a,b}(A_2)$, where X, Y and Z are in A . We have two cases for Z :

- Z invertible: then $[X:Y:Z] = [XZ^{-1}:YZ^{-1}:1]$; hence we take just $[X:Y:1]$.
- Z non invertible: So $Z = z_1\varepsilon$, see [4], in this cases we have tow cases for Y .

- Y Invertible:

Then $[X:Y:Z] = [XY^{-1}:1:ZY^{-1}]$; so we just take $[X:1:z_1\varepsilon]$; then is verified the equation of

$$E_{a,b}(A): Y^2Z + XYZ = X^3 + aX^2Z + bZ^3,$$

so we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} a &= a_0 + a_1\varepsilon \\ b &= b_0 + b_1\varepsilon \\ X &= x_0 + x_1\varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

We have:

$$z_1\varepsilon + (x_0 + x_1\varepsilon) \cdot z_1 = (x_0 + x_1\varepsilon)^3 + (a_0 + a_1\varepsilon) \cdot (x_0 + x_1\varepsilon)^2 \cdot z_1\varepsilon + (b_0 + b_1\varepsilon) \cdot z_1^3\varepsilon^3$$

which implies that

$$z_1\varepsilon + x_0z_1\varepsilon = x_0^3 + (x_0^2x_1 + a_0x_0^2z_1)\varepsilon$$

Then

$$(z_1 + x_0z_1)\varepsilon = x_0^3 + (x_0^2x_1 + a_0x_0^2z_1)\varepsilon$$

Since $(1, \epsilon)$ is a base of the vector space A over $\mathbb{F}_{2^d}$, then $x_0 = 0$, so $X = x_1\epsilon$ and $z_1\epsilon = 0$ (ie $z_1 = 0$) hence $[X: Y: Z] = [x_1\epsilon : 1 : 0]$.

- Y Non Invertible:

Then we have $Y = y_1\epsilon$, so $X = x_0 + x_1\epsilon$ is invertible so we take $[X: Y: Z] \sim [1: y_1\epsilon: z_1\epsilon]$ thus $1 + a \cdot z_1\epsilon = 0$, ie $1 + a_0z_1\epsilon = 0$ which is absurd.

Proposition 1. Every element of $E_{a,b}(A)$, is of the form $[X: Y: 1]$ or $[x\epsilon: 1: 0]$, where $x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^d}$ and we write:

$$E_{a,b}(A) = \{[X: Y: 1] \in P_2(A) | Y^2 + XY = X^3 + aX^2 + b\} \cup \{[x\epsilon: 1: 0] | x \in \mathbb{F}_{2^d}\}. [1, 4].$$

Theorem 1. Let $P = [X_1: Y_1: Z_1]$, $Q = [X_2: Y_2: Z_2]$ in $E_{a,b}(A)$ then $P + Q = [X_3: Y_3: Z_3]$:

• If $\pi_2(P) = \pi_2(Q)$ then:

$$\begin{aligned} X_3 &= X_1Y_1Y_2 + X_2Y_1^2Y_2 + X_2^2Y_1^2 + X_1X_2^2Y_1 + aX_1^2X_2Y_2 \\ &\quad + aX_1X_2^2Y_1 + aX_1^2X_2^2 + bX_1Y_1Z_2^2 \\ &\quad + bX_2Y_2Z_1^2 + bX_1^2Z_2^2 + bY_1Z_2^2Z_1 \\ &\quad + bY_2Z_1^2Z_2 + bX_1Z_2^2Z_1 \\ Y_3 &= Y_1^2Y_2^2 + X_2Y_1^2Y_2 + aX_1X_2^2Y_1 + a^2X_1^2X_2^2 + bX_1^2X_2Z_2 \\ &\quad + bX_1X_2^2Z_1 + bX_1Y_1Z_2^2 + bX_1^2Z_2^2 \\ &\quad + abX_2^2Z_1^2 + bY_1Z_2^2Z_1 + bX_1Z_2^2Z_1 \\ &\quad + abX_1Z_2^2Z_1 + abX_2Z_1^2Z_2 + b^2Z_1^2Z_2^2 \\ Z_3 &= X_1^2X_2Y_2 + X_1X_2^2Y_1 + Y_1^2Y_2Z_2 + Y_1Y_2^2Z_1 + X_1^2X_2^2 \\ &\quad + X_2Y_1^2Z_2 + X_1^2Y_2Z_2 + aX_1^2Y_2Z_2 + aX_2^2Y_1Z_1 \\ &\quad + X_1^2X_2Z_2 + aX_1X_2^2Z_1 + bY_1Z_2^2Z_1 \\ &\quad + bY_2Z_1^2Z_2 + bX_1Z_2^2Z_1 \end{aligned}$$

• If $\pi_2(P) \neq \pi_2(Q)$ then:

$$\begin{aligned} X_3 &= X_1Y_2^2Z_1 + X_2Y_1^2Z_2 + X_1^2Y_2Z_2 + X_2^2Y_1Z_1 + aX_1^2X_2Z_2 \\ &\quad + aX_1X_2^2Z_1 + bX_1Z_2^2Z_1 + bX_2Z_1^2Z_2 \\ Y_3 &= X_1^2X_2Y_2 + X_1X_2^2Y_1 + Y_1^2Y_2Z_2 + Y_1Y_2^2Z_1 + X_1^2Y_2Z_2 \\ &\quad + X_2^2Y_1Z_1 + aX_1^2Y_2Z_2 + aX_2^2Y_1Z_1 \\ &\quad + aX_1^2X_2Z_2 + aX_1X_2^2Z_1 + bY_1Z_2^2Z_1 \\ &\quad + bY_2Z_1^2Z_2 + bX_1Z_2^2Z_1 + bX_2Z_1^2Z_2 \\ Z_3 &= X_1^2X_2Z_2 + X_1X_2^2Z_1 + Y_1^2Z_2^2 + Y_2^2Z_1^2 + X_1Y_1Z_2^2 \\ &\quad + X_2Y_2Z_1^2 + aX_1^2Z_2^2 + aX_2^2Z_1^2 \end{aligned}$$

Proof: Using the explicit formulas in [8] we prove the theorem.

IV. CRYPTOGRAPHY APPLICATION

Let $P \in E_{a,b}(A_n)$ of order ρ , we will use the subgroup $\langle P \rangle$ of $E_{a,b}(A_n)$ to encrypt message, and we denote $G = \langle P \rangle$.

• Coding of Elements of G .

We will give a code to each element $Q = m \cdot P \in G$, where $m \in \{1, 2, \dots, \rho\}$.

Let $Q = [\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i \epsilon^i : \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_i \epsilon^i : Z]$ where, $x_i, y_i \in \mathbb{F}_{2^d}$, for $i = 0, 1, \dots, n-1$ and $Z = \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} z_i \epsilon^i$, or $Z = 1$.

We set:

$$x_i = c_{0,i} + c_{1,i}\alpha + \dots + c_{(d-1),i}\alpha^{d-1} = c_{0,i}c_{1,i} \dots c_{(d-1),i}$$

where α is a primitive root of an irreducible polynomial of degree d over $\mathbb{F}_2$ then, we code Q as it follows:[6]

• If $Q = [\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} x_i \epsilon^i : \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} y_i \epsilon^i : 1]$, then:

$$Q = \underbrace{x_0x_1 \dots x_{n-1}y_0y_1 \dots y_{n-1}10 \dots 0}_{3.d.n}$$

• If $Q = [\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} x_i \epsilon^i : 1 : \sum_{i=3}^{n-1} z_i \epsilon^i]$, then:

$$Q = \underbrace{0 \dots 0x_1 \dots x_{n-1}10 \dots 0z_3 \dots z_{n-1}}_{3.d.n}$$

• Exchange of Secret Key

Alice and Bob wants exchange the secret key, for this he start publicly with integer d , a curve elliptic $E_{a,b}(A_n)$, a point $P \in E_{a,b}(A_n)$ of order ρ and the coding methode over $G = \langle P \rangle$.

Alice chooses a random number $0 \leq t \leq \rho - 1$ and computes $K = tP$.

Alice sends K to Bob, but keep t

Bob chooses a random number $0 \leq l \leq \rho - 1$, computes $K' = lP$.

Bob sends K' to Alice, but keep l .

Alice computes $t \cdot K' = t \cdot lP$.

Bob computes $l \cdot K = l \cdot tP$.

Finally, Alice and Bob are agree with a point $S = t \cdot lP$, choose the binary code of point S as a private key, which transformed on the decimal code « S' ».

Remark 1. With the secret key S' such as the decimal code of point S Alice and Bob can encrypt and decrypt the message (m).

• ECC Key Generation Block Diagram

Fig. 1 Depict the key generation phase

To encrypt P_m , a user picks an integer « r » at random and sends the point $(r \cdot Q, P_m + r \cdot Pbkey)$. This operation is showed in Fig. 2.

• ECC Encryption Process Block Diagram

Decryption this message is done by multiplying the first component of the received point by the secret key « S' » and subtract it from the second component:

$$(P_m + r \cdot Pbkey) - S' \cdot (r \cdot Q) = P_m + r \cdot S' \cdot Q - S' \cdot r \cdot Q = P_m$$

This operation is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2 The encryption operation

Fig. 3 Decrypting the message

• Example.

For the example we take the case $n = 3$ (i.e.: $E_{a,b}(A_3)$) and let α is a primitive root of an irreducible polynomial $R(X) = X^3 + X + 1$ over $\mathbb{F}_2$.

We consider the field $\mathbb{F}_2(\alpha) = \frac{\mathbb{F}_2[X]}{(R(X))} \cong \mathbb{F}_8$, $\mathbb{F}_8$ is the finite field of order 2^3 and of basis $(1, \alpha, \alpha^2)$.

Let $a = 1 + \alpha + \alpha\epsilon + \epsilon^2$, $b = 1 + \alpha^2\epsilon + \epsilon^2$ two elements of A_3 .

The elliptic curve $E_{a,b}(A_3)$ has 896 elements but the elliptic curve $E_{a_0,b_0}(\mathbb{F}_8)$, where $a_0 = \pi(a)$, and $b_0 = \pi(b)$ has 14 elements.

So, we have well: $\#E_{a,b}(A_3) = \#E_{a_0,b_0}(\mathbb{F}_8) \times \#\mathbb{F}_8^2$.

We consider the point $P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2 + \epsilon: 1]$, we have $G = \langle P \rangle$ is the subgroup of order 56 so, for $Q \in G, \exists m \in \{1, 2, \dots, 56\}: Q = mP$.

The points of G are:

- $P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2 + \epsilon: 1]$
- $2P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha + (\alpha^2 + 1)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $3P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (\alpha + 1) + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $4P = [1 + \alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $5P = [\alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon: 1]$
- $6P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon: 1]$
- $7P = [\alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $8P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: 1 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$

- $9P = [\alpha + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + (\alpha^2 + \alpha)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $10P = [1 + \alpha + \epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $11P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $12P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $13P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $14P = [\alpha^2\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1: 0]$
- $15P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2 + (\alpha^2 + \alpha)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $16P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: \alpha + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2) + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $17P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $18P = [1 + \alpha + \epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $19P = [\alpha + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon: 1]$
- $20P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $21P = [\alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $22P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon: 1 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $23P = [\alpha + \epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $24P = [1 + \alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + \epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $25P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: \alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $26P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $27P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $28P = [(\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1: 0]$
- $29P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2 + \epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $30P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $31P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $32P = [1 + \alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $33P = [\alpha + \epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $34P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $35P = [\alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $36P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $37P = [\alpha + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $38P = [1 + \alpha + \epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon: 1]$
- $39P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon: 1]$
- $40P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $41P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $42P = [\alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1: 0]$
- $43P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha^2 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon: 1]$
- $44P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: \alpha + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $45P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $46P = [1 + \alpha + \epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $47P = [\alpha + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2) + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $48P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: \alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \epsilon^2: 1]$
- $49P = [\alpha^2\epsilon + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $50P = [1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha^2\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $51P = [\alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $52P = [1 + \alpha + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2 + \epsilon + (1 + \alpha)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $53P = [\alpha + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: \alpha^2\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $54P = [1 + \alpha^2 + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon + (\alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1 + \alpha + \alpha^2 + \alpha\epsilon + (1 + \alpha + \alpha^2)\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $55P = [\alpha^2 + \alpha^2\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1 + (1 + \alpha^2)\epsilon + \alpha\epsilon^2: 1]$
- $56P = [0: 1: 0]$

• Table of Coding the Elements of $\mathbb{G}$

We use English letters for this application. The coding are as follows:

TABLE I
 TABLE OF LETTERS

Code of m.P	Symbol
00100101010110000010000000	a
10111101101010110010000000	b
01111101101110001100000000	c
11001101111111011000000000	d
01000001101101100010000000	e
11101000101111100010000000	f
00000110110010110010000000	g
11111011010001101010000000	h
01011011000101100110000000	i
11010011100110101110000000	j
01101000100011111110000000	k
10110110011101011100000000	l
00101010010000110010000000	m
00000110010000000000000000	n
00101000110101110010000000	o
10110101001011111110000000	p
01101001101110101110000000	q
11010001111100101110000000	r
01011000101110100010000000	s
11111011101110101010000000	t
00000110110010001010000000	u
11101000100101110100000000	v
01000010000101101110000000	w
11001111001100101100000000	x
01111100100000110110000000	y
10111101111010111100000000	z
00100111100101011100000000	(
00000001110000000000000000	)
00100111101100100100000000	;
10111101010101010100000000	!
01111100101110100100000000	:
110011111111101010000000	\$
010000100010111110000000	.
111010000011111010000000	@
00000110110010111110000000	>
111110111000110110000000	<
01011000100101100110000000	%
11010001100110100010000000	£
01101001100011100010000000	\$
10110101011101010110000000	/
00101000110000110110000000	?
00000111110000000000000000	
00101010010101100010000000	#
10110110001011100110000000	0
011010001011101101000000	1
11010011111001100100000000	2
01011011001110111100000000	3
11111011001110110010000000	4
00000110110010001100000000	5
11101000110010001100000000	6
01000001100101101110000000	7
11001101100110011010000000	8
01111101100000101010000000	9
10111101111010111100000000	,
00100101010010101010000000	space
00000000100000000000000000	~

• Encryption and Decryption Messages

Let the following message: “nlmad tamazivt”

Transmutation this message effected letter by letter, its points codes are:

TABLE II
 TABLE OF ENCRYPT

Code of letters	Symbol
00100101010110000010000000	a
11001101111111101100000000	d
00101010010000110010000000	m
00000110010000000000000000	n
11111011101110101010000000	t
00000110110010001010000000	u
11101000100101110100000000	v
10111101111010111100000000	z
10110110011101010110000000	l
01011011000101100110000000	i

The encryption and decryption of these points are effected by the process cited before see, Figs. 1 and 2.

Exchange of Secret Key.

Alice chooses a random number $t = 5$ and computes $K = t.P$.

Alice sends K to Bob, but keep t

Bob chooses a random number $= 7$, computes $K' = l.P$.

Bob sends K' to Alice, but keep l .

Alice computes $tK' = 35P$.

Bob computes $lK = 35P$.

Alice and Bob are agree with a point $S = 35P$, choose the code of point S as a private key, which transformed on the decimal code $S' = 3563264$

To encrypt every point P_m , a user picks an integer « r » at random and sends the point $(r.Q, P_m + r.Pbkey)$.

We have the following text:

(10111101101010110010000000,01111101101111000110000000)(1100110111111110110000000,01000001101101100010000000)(1110100010111100010000000,00000110110010110010000000)(11111011010001101010000000,01011011000101100110000000)(11010011100110101110000000,0,0110100010001111110000000)(101101100111010110000000,0010101001000110010000000)(00000110010000000000,00101000110101110010000000)

(10111101101010110010000000,01111101101111000110000000)(1100110111111110110000000,01000001101101100010000000)(1110100010111100010000000,00000110110010110010000000)(11111011010001101010000000,01011011000101100110000000)(11010011100110101110000000,0,0110100010001111110000000)(101101100111010110000000,0010101001000110010000000)(00000110010000000000,00101000110101110010000000)

Remark 2. With this application, we can encrypt and decrypt any message. The security of this encryption is based on the discrete logarithm problem.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have studied the elliptic curves cryptography over the ring $A_n = \mathbb{F}_{2^d}[\epsilon]$; $\epsilon^n = 0$, and we have established the coding over the elliptic curves $E_{a,b}(A_n)$.

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Further, the Discrete Logarithm Problem (DLP) on this elliptic curve is equivalent to the one on $E_{a_0, b_0}(\mathbb{F}_{2^d})$ but the cardinal of this elliptic curve is bigger than that of $E_{a_0, b_0}(\mathbb{F}_{2^d})$, which seems to be beneficial and interesting in cryptography.

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